

RECYCLING OF CEMENT KILN DUST FOR CARBON SEQUESTRATION- A REVIEW

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Abstract

Cement kiln dust (CKD) is an industrial by-product of cement factories generated during cement manufacture and is a waste material that needs to be landfilled. Cement kiln dust is a pollutant that affects the soil, plant, and water ecosystem. Cement kiln dust contains a higher content of potassium, chlorides, and sulfates. Hence, this makes them unsuitable for reuse again in the production of cement. It also has silica, Ca, and Mg. Recycling of CKD for reclamation of problem soil, stabilization of heavy metals, carbon sequestration with more phytolith production, and treatment of acidic effluent needs emphasis. More research needs to be conducted along the above lines.

Key words: landfills, stabilization, phytolith,

Introduction

The cement industry in India is one of the seventeen most polluting industries concerned the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) of the significant emission of mineral dust (Duszak *et al.*, 2015). The primary environmental concern of cement production is issues related to mining raw materials, energy consumption, and air emissions (Udara *et al.*, 2019). To produce one ton of cement, around 0.06-0.07 tonnes of CKD is produced (Elbaz *et al.*, 2019). Global cement production will increase from 3.27 to 4.83 billion metric tons around 2030 AD. From this, about 220 million tons of cement kiln dust are discarded annually from these cement manufacturing facilities. X-ray diffraction analysis of cement kiln dust showed that the main constituent is calcite (CaCO₃), quartz (SiO₂), and calcium sulfate (CaSO₄) (Aboufotouh and Dohdoh, 2017).

Cement kiln dust (CKD) is an industrial by-product of cement factories generated during cement manufacture and is a waste material that needs to be landfilled. It is a fine powdery material similar in appearance to Portland cement (Arulrajah *et al.*, 2017). The exhaust gases from the cement production process pass through a dust collection system (e.g., cyclone).

CKD is a non-hazardous material due to its low leaching properties for heavy metals (Rehman *et al.* 2011). Trace constituents include cadmium; lead, selenium, and radionuclide are generally found at concentrations of less than 0.05 percent by weight in CKD. However, since these constituents are potentially toxic (concentration can vary between cement plants), it is essential to assess the mobility and leachability of these trace constituents in the CKD (Usdot, 1998). The objective of the review was to collect information on the following topics the effect of CKD on plants, CKD use in wastewater treatment, and CKD use in an agricultural field.

Effects of cement kiln dust on plants

Prasad and Inamdar (1990) reported that dusting of CKD on black gram (*Vigna mungo*) plants decreased the plant height, phytomass, net primary productivity and chlorophyll content, size and the number of flowers leading to yield reduction.

The water content of leaves found constantly decreases with increasing cement kiln content in the pots. The decrease in moisture content might be due to the cement kiln dust generated as a by-product rich in K⁺, SO₄⁻, and other compounds (Ismet *et al.*, 2012).

Emissions from cement industries deteriorate air quality and degrade human health. Emissions have local and global environmental impacts resulting in global warming, ozone depletion, acid rain, biodiversity loss, and reduction in crop productivity, *etc.*,

CKD use in wastewater treatment

Due to the calcium oxide (CaO) content of CKD, it has future potential as a replacement for lime in treating acidic wastewater such as acid rock drainage. CKD with low free lime contents neutralizes the acidic effluent. (Mackie *et al.*, 2010).

CKD reuse in the agricultural field

The chemical and physical properties of CKD provide various advantages for agricultural applications as dust could supply plants

with enough amounts of S, Mg, and K, so they use CKD in the place of chemical fertilizer with increased yields of alfalfa. Calcium silicate and lime content of CKD increased the dry matter yield of sorghum in acid soil. CKD contained beneficial amounts of crop micro- and macro-nutrients, providing calcium to potatoes as an efficient source of plant-available potassium comparable to commercial fertilizers without resulting in crop or soil contamination with heavy metals. Due to its ability to hold water from 40 to 50% of its weight, CKD can assist in drought resistance. The alkalinity nature of CKD can increase the pH of the soils and reduce fluctuations in plant and root stress (Prabakaran, 2019). Hence, CKD could be an alkali amendment in acidic soils (Christie, 2001). Bio-solids mixed with CKD can be recycled as agricultural amendments through direct applications to croplands with some environmental and health (Dudka and Miller, 1999). The liming and fertilizer value of alkaline-stabilized biosolids using CKD applied annually to spring barley crops produced a nutrient value similar to an inorganic fertilizer (Christie *et al.*, 2001). Cement kiln dust is a potential source for the reclamation of acidic soils. Soil extractable K and Ca increased rapidly due to the cement kiln dust applications. Soil metal contents decreased from initial soil levels and were lower than norms (maximum permissible limit). Increase in potato tuber yield at an increased rate of cement kiln dust and synthetic fertilizers application. The K and Mg uptake by plants increased with cement kiln dust and commercial fertilizers. The specific gravity of potato tuber decreased with the highest commercial fertilizers and cement kiln dust rates (Lafond and Simard, 1999).

Surface-applied CKD increased forage yield. In addition, the concentration and accumulation of macronutrients *viz.*, N, P, K, Ca, and Mg; micronutrients *viz.* Mn, Cu, Zn, and B increased in the forage tissue. CKD is quickly available source of Ca and K than lime (Rodd *et al.* 2010).

Silica and phytolith

Phytoliths are ultra particles of silica (between 5 and 100 μm) that form within most plants. Phytoliths form in different shapes and sizes and are stable in most sediment and soil. Grasses accumulate phytoliths as inter and internal amorphous silica in the form of silicic acid by precipitation and polymerization. These particles encompass a variety of ultrastructures depending on the cell type in which the silica is deposited (Zancajo *et al.*, 2019).

Application of silica fertilizer significantly increased the content of the rice phytoliths in the stem, leaf and sheath in Si-deficient soil while more accumulation of phytolith was recorded in Silica enriched paddy soils (Sun *et al.*, 2109).

Conclusion: The cement kiln dust has rich in silica, calcium, magnesium, and potassium. Hence it needs to be used for the reclamation of sodic soil, acid sulfate soil, sequestration Carbon as phytolith, and phytolith occluded carbon (PhytOC), *etc.*, For treating the acidic industrial effluent (like a distillery, waste battery recycling, *etc.*) CKD is a potential resource. The increased potassium content of the soil due to the application of cement kiln dust will increase the

yield and quality of the crop. Hence, this will also reduce the dependency on imported potassic fertilizers. The CKD is rich in silica, hence exploration is needed to estimate the availability of soil silica and the accumulation of amorphous silica needs to be studied. Phytolith is rich in silica and is ideal for long-term carbon sequestration needed further exploration. The works of literature regarding the utilization of CKD for agricultural and environmental application needs further exploration. Hence, more research is possible along the above lines.

Conflict of interest The study did not invoke any animal, hence no conflict of interest.

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